

Isolation, Selection and Molecular Identification of Keratinase-Producing Yeast from Feather Waste Environment

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Abstract

Processing of poultries generates large quantities of protein-rich feather wastes whose disposal causes environmental challenges. Keratinolytic yeasts produce keratinase enzymes, which are vital for degrading the highly recalcitrant keratin structure. However, production of keratinase from yeasts has remained largely unexplored. This investigation focused on the isolation, screening for keratinase and molecular identification of yeast from feather waste environment. Using standard microbiological procedures, yeasts were isolated from feather dump site, screened, and identified using molecular methods involving genomic DNA extraction, PCR amplification and nucleotide sequencing. Identified yeast isolates were *Yarrowia galli*, *Candida sp*, *Candida tropicalis* and *Saccharomyces diastaticus*. *Yarrowia lipolytica* which was subsequently confirmed as *Yarrowia galli* via molecular methods, has the maximum keratinase activity of 0.52 u/mL and highest percentage feather degradation rate of 41.8 %. This study demonstrates that the yeast isolated from feather waste has potential applications in biodegradation of feathers, waste management, and industrial biotechnology. The use of molecular techniques ensures accurate identification of yeast species.

Keywords Enzyme, Feathers, keratinase, Keratinolytic yeast, *Yarrowia galli*

Introduction

Keratin is a highly stable fibrous protein that forms the major component of hair, feathers, nails, horns, and the outer covering of vertebrates (Leslie et al., 2021). It possesses a high concentration of cysteine concentration, which form disulfide linkage that confer mechanical strength, rigidity, and resistance to chemical and enzymatic degradation (Khan et al., 2024). Keratin is broadly classified into α -keratins, present in mammals and having fibrous and helical structures (da Silva, 2018). For example, in hair, skin, and wool, and β -keratins found in birds and reptiles, acquired in parallel polypeptide chains in claws, scales, beaks, skin, and feathers (da Silva, 2018). Due to its recalcitrant nature, keratin-rich wastes such as feathers accumulate as environmental pollutants especially in poultry sites (Anbesaw, 2022).

They are complex cutaneous structure composed primarily of keratin. Chicken feathers provide coverage and protection for most parts of a bird's body (Kurien et al., 2022). In recent years, attention has shifted toward the sustainable valorization of poultry feathers through biological and enzymatic approaches (Aradoaei, 2024). Admasie et al. (2024) had proved that chicken feathers can be effectively hydrolyzed by microbial keratinases into soluble peptides and amino acids.

Keratinolysis is a multi-enzyme process which involves the coordinated activity of keratinases, disulfide reductases and other proteases to disrupt disulfide bonds and hydrolyze keratin into soluble peptide and amino acids (Jiang et al., 2025). Keratinases are predominantly produced by microorganisms, which includes species of *Bacillus*, *Streptomyces*, *Aspergillus* and *Actinomyces* (Ezeme-Nwafor & George-Okafor 2022; Moskaluk et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2024; Mozejko & Bohacz, 2024).

Only a few studies have examined production of keratinase from yeast, although numerous investigations have documented keratinase-producing bacteria and mold. Yeasts are ubiquitous free-living fungi that are inexpensive to cultivate. They are well-known for recombinant protein expression (Oloye et al., 2025) Additionally, because of their distinct genetic and physiological composition, they are known for their wide variety of application. (Adelabu et al., 2024).

Khan et al. (2024) had isolated keratinolytic bacteria from dumpsites. Otuyelu et al. (2025) also screened and identified keratinase degrading molds isolated from soil collected at various chicken feathers waste disposal sites within Ilorin metropolis, but few studies have reported yeast as keratinolytic organism; hence our interest in yeast as keratinase-producing microorganism. In this study, keratinolytic yeasts was isolated from soil sample obtained from poultry feathers dump site, screened for keratinase production, and then identified.

Materials and methods

Sample collection

Soil and feather samples were aseptically collected from different poultry waste dump sites, labelled, and taken to laboratory for storage in refrigeration until usage. All collection sites were within Abeokuta metropolis, Ogun state, Nigeria.

Feather meal powder preparation

The whole feathers were thoroughly washed 3-4times with distilled water to remove impurities. They were defatted by soaking for 24 hr in ethanol concentration of 70% followed by rinsing with distilled water, after which they were oven-dried at 140 °C for 48 hr (Otuyelu et al., 2025). Treated feathers were milled into fine powder using electric grinder (Philips INO23) and sterilized at 121 °C for 15 min (Otuyelu et al., 2025).

Isolation of Yeast

Petri dishes containing sterile Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose Agar (YEPDA) and 1% Chloramphenicol and Streptomycin were used to plate dilutions of 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} of the serially diluted soil sample. At 30 °C, inoculated agar plates were incubated for 72 hr (Adelabu & Kareem, 2022). Morphological characteristics of the yeasts were examined, and biochemical tests were carried out on the yeast isolates for phenotypic identification (Barnett et al., 2000).

Screening of yeast for keratinolytic enzyme

Skimmed milk agar medium was used for qualitative screening. The agar medium contained 3.0 g yeast extract, 1.0 g dextrose, 5.0 g peptone 1.0 g skimmed milk Powder and 15.0 g agar while pH was maintained at 4.5 using phosphate buffer. All the ingredients of skimmed

milk agar medium were sterilized in an autoclave except skimmed milk powder which was added separately. Isolated yeasts were subculture on skimmed milk agar plates and were incubated for 72 hr at 30 °C (Khan et al., 2024). Quantitative screening was carried out with feather medium comprising of feather meal 10g, NaCl 0.1g, K₂HPO₄ 0.076g, KH₂PO₄ 0.08g, MgCl₂.6H₂O 0.04g, Glucose 1g Yeast extract 0.02g (Abdelmoteleb et al., 2023). The medium was inoculated with yeast and incubated at 150 rpm for 14 d with a shaker incubator set at 30 °C (Aishwath, 2024). Quantity of keratinase produced was determined by the method of Otuyelu et al. (2025).

Percentage Feather degradation rate

This was carried out following the method of Otuyelu et al. (2025). Ten grams of feather was added to 100 mL mineral salt medium. After incubation for 14 d. The medium was filtered, and the feathers washed in distilled water. It was dried and weight loss was calculated. Yeast that shows the highest degradation rate was selected and identified using molecular method.

Percentage degradation of feather

$$= \frac{(\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}) \times 100}{\text{Initial weight}}$$

Selection of Yeast culture

The yeast with the best keratinolytic activity and percentage feather degradation rate was selected for further study and identified using molecular tools.

Molecular Identification

Genomic DNA extraction

Yeast DNAs were extracted using the protocol stated by Adelabu et al. (2024). Isolation of yeast DNA was performed with Zymo DNA extraction kit following instruction manual. The Thermo Scientific NANODROP (ND 1000) Spectrophotometer was used to measure the concentration and purity of DNA (Adelabu et al., 2024).

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) and Gene Sequencing

The extracted genomic DNA was subjected to PCR amplification of internal transcribed spacer region of the rRNA gene using the primers ITS1 (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') and ITS4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3'). Amplicons were separated on a 1.5% agarose gel for size

determination, followed by sequencing using the Sanger's method (Chanu et al., 2022)

Analysis of Data

Experiments were performed in triplicate, with data presented as mean ± standard deviation, analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS v17.0 was used to analysed data. DNA sequence was identified with BLAST (NCBI) while phylogenetic and evolutionary analysis were conducted with Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) version 10 (MEGA X) software (Adelabu et al. 2024).

Results and Discussion

Isolation and phenotypic characterization of yeast isolates

Four (4) morphologically well-formed single colonies were isolated. Isolated yeasts tested positive for urease, 10% NaCl, 5% Glucose and ethanol but negative for 50% glucose, and lactose (data not shown). The yeast isolates were identified using physiological and biochemical methods as *Yarrowia lipolytica*, later identified as *Y. galli* using molecular tools. *Candida* spp, *Candida tropicalis*, and *Saccharomyces diastaticus*. Studies have shown that these yeasts thrive well in environments with high temperature and low pH (Adelabu et al., 2024), hence their presence in keratin-enriched soil. Report has shown that *Yarrowia galli* can be found in nutrient-enriched contaminated environment such as meat processing environment (Saraiva et al., 2025).

Screening of yeasts for Keratinase enzyme production

All tested yeasts were positive for keratinase enzyme by displaying clear halo formation on skimmed milk agar (Figure 1). This could be due to the presence of nitrogen source; casein present in skimmed milk used for qualitative screening (Ezeme-Nwafor & George-Okafor, 2022). The study of Parmar & Trivedi, (2021) also supported the fact that nitrogen is integral to Keratinase synthesis when peptone and yeast extract as nitrogen sources yielded the highest enzyme production. Keratinase-positive yeasts shown clearance zone from 7.9 mm to 27.0 mm in diameter. Among the isolates, *Yarrowia galli* produced the largest zones of clearance (27.05

mm), followed by *Candida* sp (18.26 mm) while *Saccharomyces diastaticus* had the lowest (7.93 mm) (Table 1). These findings suggest that *Y.galli* and other yeasts produce extracellular keratin-degrading proteases that hydrolyze keratin peptide bonds, leading to the secretion of amino acids and low-molecular-weight peptides (Moktip et al., 2025). Quantitative screening showed that all the yeast isolates produced keratinase at different levels of enzyme (Table 1). The highest keratinase activity was produced by

Yarrowia galli (0.52 U/mL), and then *Candida tropicalis* (0.48 U/mL), *Candida* sp has 0.32 U/mL enzyme activity while *Saccharomyces diastaticus* has the lowest level of keratinase activity (0.30 U/mL). According to reports, different *Candida* species could secrete keratin disulfide reductase which breaks down disulfide bonds and convert them to thiol groups. This enzymatic reaction makes keratin containing materials more accessible to the enzyme (Duarte et al., 2011).

Fig. 1 Keratinase producing yeast showing zones of clearance

Table 1: Qualitative screening of yeast isolates in feather meal medium

Organisms	Zones of clearance in (mm)	Enzyme activity (U/mL)
<i>Yarrowia galli</i>	27.05±0.13	0.52
<i>Candida spp</i>	18.26±0.1	0.48
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	15.07±0.01	0.30
<i>Saccharomyces diastaticus</i>	7.93±0.12	0.32

Percentage Feather degradation rate

Degradation of the chicken feather by the yeasts is shown in Table 4. Gradual degradation of the feather was observed after incubation at 30°C for 14 d. Most of the feather was degraded after 10 d except the shaft which degraded completely after 14 d of incubation. Results shows that *Yarrowia galli* has the highest percentage feather degradation rate with possible indication that this

yeast might have secreted leucin aminopeptidase more than other yeasts tested for percentage rate of degradation (Liu et al., 2025). Least feather degradation rate was observed with *Saccharomyces diastaticus* showing that, this yeast might have low keratin degradation due to disulphide bond-reducing activity leading to reduction of disulfide bonds found between cysteine residue in keratin (Breakspear et al., 2024).

Table 2 Percentage feather degradation rate

Organisms	Initial feather	Final feather	Percentage
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	weight (g)	weight (g)	degradation (%)
<i>Yarrowia galli</i>	10	5.82	41.8
<i>Candida sp</i>	10	7.90	21.00
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	10	7.64	23.60
<i>Saccharomyces diastaticus</i>	10	8.79	12.10

Molecular identification of selected yeast isolate
Table 3 shows the result of molecular identification of the yeast isolate with maximum keratinase activity and rate of feather degradation. *Yarrowia galli* identified with PCR was earlier identified as *Yarrowia lipolytica* with biochemical characterization. Gene sequencing analysis revealed a 99.09% sequence identity corresponding to the NCBI accession number HQ914910.1. Figure 2 illustrate the PCR products separated by gel electrophoresis which showed that the gene was approximately 1000base pairs in length. Evolutionary relationships were inferred

using the Neighbor-Joining method. The optimal phylogenetic tree (Figure 3) has a branch length of 0.21034120 and was identified as *Yarrowia galli*. As observed in this present study, molecular approaches employing DNA extraction, PCR amplification, and sequencing offer higher precision in yeast identification compared to conventional phenotypic characterization (Kahve et al., 2022). This supports previous observation by Oloye et al. (2025) where polymerase chain reaction-based method was used to identify laccase producing bacteria obtained from the wastewater of a paint manufacturing industry.

Table 3: Identity of yeast strain by sequence of genomic DNA

Isolate	Accession no NCBI	Name of organism	Identity
Y1	HQ914910.1	<i>Yarrowia galli</i>	99.09%

Figure 2: Agarose gel electrophoresis showing amplified 18S rDNA gene of *Yarrowia galli* isolate

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